

The Essence of the Concept of Family Life in Modern Psychology

Razakova Raykhan Saylaubekovna ¹, Sherzhanova Nodira Alisherovna ²,

Solayev Og'abek Ilhombek o'g'li ³

¹ Associate professor, Department of "Pedagogy and psychology", Urgench State University, Uzbekistan, Urgench

^{2, 3} Teacher, Department of "Pedagogy and psychology", Urgench State University, Uzbekistan, Urgench

Abstract:

This article examines the meaning of the concept of family life in modern psychology.

Keywords: Complementary relations, environment, problem, personality, family social concepts, ethnicity, couple, conflict, element, education.

Enter. The analysis of scientific literature on the studied problem showed that there are problems related to family life and they remain relevant in all periods, attracting the attention of various researchers. Today, this concept is interpreted in various ways. There are many studies logically devoted to the study of this phenomenon of family, marriage, development of family relations and from different points of view. We believe that it is appropriate to disclose [1].

According to many researchers, the modern family as a micro-society of the whole society manifests all its needs and interests, as well as reflects all its changes. On the other hand, family life is dynamic, because it has characteristics that apply to the entire stage of society's development, among which socio-psychological characteristics are the leading ones.

According to E. G. Eidemiller, V. Yustitskyi, the family is a small social group, as any element of society, it differs in its character of unity. The important social necessity of the family is that its disappearance can lead to the disappearance of the whole humanity [2].

Analysis of literature on the topic. Today, the problems of family and human relations are ancient and relevant. Ancient scholars, philosophers, scientific writers, and modern researchers have paid

attention to this area of life. It was studied in a broad sense from the point of view of the process of formation of personality in the family . G. B. Shoumarov, V.M. Karimova, I.Y. Yokubov, E.G'. Goziev, B.R. Kodirov, O.M. Musurmonova, who conducted a lot of research in this direction by the mature psychologists of our Republic on the psychology of family and interpersonal relations, social and generational factors in the growth of a person, R.S. Samarov, B.M. Umarov, O'B. Shamsiev, N.A. Soginov, F.A. Akramova, N.N. Salaeva, N.X. Lutfullaeva, O.A. Abdusattorova, X.R. Khaidarova and others have been studied and are being studied.

According to G.B. Shoumarov, I.O. Xaydarov, N.A. Soginov and others, the family is based on marriage or blood kinship, family members are connected by marriage, common living, common interests, feelings, aspirations, and a system of connections, partnerships, and relationships in which the individual and the needs of society are met. The concept of marriage, as a rule, is explained in the form of a separate connection between a man and a woman for the purpose of mutual benefit, birth and upbringing of future children, continuation of the family, running a common household, living together, etc. [3].

V.M. Karimova's research shows that the family is a more complex and multifaceted system of relationships than marriage, because in most cases it includes not only partners, that is, husband and wife, but also their children, as well as other also unites relatives. In addition, the family, according to the authors, in its essence, is very close to the general model of the entire society in which it operates. Generations of people are exchanged through the family, a person is born in it, and through it the lineage continues. Marital-family relations, as an important sphere of a person's life, determine his quality of life, make up his life area, and become an area of manifestation of his identity as a person. In this case, certain characteristics of the emergence and functioning of the family institution depend on the peculiarities of modern life.

The research work of Professor V.M. Karimova in her doctoral thesis is the social and psychological concepts of the family and its surroundings, i.e. sexual socialization, gender differences, femininity and masculinity qualities, and the formation of perceptions of parent-child interactions. - being related to the analysis of psychological characteristics was added to the science by introducing the concepts of family social imagination (OIT) to Uzbek psychology.

In particular, V.M. Karimova shows several stages of the formation of ideas about the family and its values:

1. The general social sphere of the formation of family imaginations.
2. Ethical-normative aspect of family imagination.
3. Legal sphere of family roles.
4. Economic aspects of family roles.
5. The reproductive aspect of family roles [1] .

Family social imagination is a complex psychological system with a complex character, which includes family relationships and all the knowledge and concepts that are formed about them.

In the framework of special psychology and family psychology, the research works carried out by G.B.Shoumarov and his followers are of practical importance due to their originality.

G. B. Shoumarov's research work shows a number of features of the problems of young families. Including:

- the significance of the period of formation of sexual and role relations of a young couple to concretely determine the functions of a young family;
- socio-psychological characteristics of a young family are more widely and individually observed and formed;

- the child's personality;
- the role and importance of parents in the formation of a child's personality;
- some features of the parents' family (one child, parents' lack of education, lack of communication culture, unhappiness, etc.)

economic poverty and housing shortage are focused on[3].

Results and discussion . Thus, today the family is gaining independent importance as an important institution for the organization of personal and family well-being. Instead of traditional roles, there was a smooth, strapping cooperation based on the commonality of goals, needs, views and feelings of relationships and activities. Such activity is becoming not only an ideal, but also a reality for a growing number of families and an important characteristic of a new type of family.

O.G. Prokhorova emphasizes that today the family is a unique social institution, a mediator between man and society. Through it, the main values are passed from generation to generation, it is in the family environment that the powerful power of influencing the process of social development, production and the emergence of relations in society is concentrated[4].

According to L.B. Sneider, the family can be considered as a social institution only when it is characterized by the three main forms of family relations, that is, marriage, fatherhood and kinship ties. If there is not at least one of these indicators, then it is appropriate to use the concept of family group. In addition, according to the scientist, the family emerges as a spiritual and moral union consisting of partners and relatives, which are not only related to a common place of residence and economic dependence, but also to emotional feelings and special relationships [5].

M. Warden, A. Varga consider the family as a single whole, psychological, biological organism system, which has separate, but interrelated subsystems, among which:

polygamy , i.e., partner behavior of spouses is manifested as a model of mutual sexual relations, which is very important for the formation of couples;

parenthood, that is, related to the tasks of caring for and raising children, such as the model of mastering the roles of future fathers and mothers;

Each of the subsystems is considered very important in the formation and emergence of partners, serving as a model for learning. Parents - negative relationships in the child system (bad relationship with one or both parents, lack of parental support for children, belief in oneself as defective) to other people, own parents and relatives, later, it becomes the primary cause of aggression against the spouse.

UAKulakova, under the term family, suggests understanding a small social group based on the organization and management of a joint life and economy, consisting of emotional-significant relationships between its members, each of which has the power to move the personal development of each of them [6] .

S.A. Vekilova, V.Kalliakmanis say that the family is an open, self-organizing system, an integrated organization that is constantly interacting with the outside world and has a set of interrelated elements. they count. When considering the family, the authors distinguish its dimensions, laws of operation, life cycle stages. Family life is subject to the following laws:

homeostasis, according to which each system strives to maintain its position, strives for stability of its main indicators;

development, according to which any family strives to go through a full life cycle, at each stage of which special tasks aimed at maintaining the vital activity of the system are solved.

Each person becomes a free creator of his life, his social environment. In this regard, the concept of family is manifested in the process of family life, in which a person creates a long and strong relationship against various life difficulties with his environment. Taking into account the three criteria identified by the authors (solidity, care, closeness), family life is necessarily manifested by being in a long-term patronage relationship with a common residential area, but also not in spending a certain amount of time together as such. That is, in contrast to the traditional study of the family, the author emphasizes that joint family life is a process, active participation of partners in each other's lives, mutual attention and family relationships develop, special emphasis on a specific area where family life is carried out he gives

Summary. Thus, based on the above, the analysis of scientific literature on the studied problem shows the high relevance of studying issues related to family life, in which couple relations, the process of family relations, social - psychological adaptation is one of the main problems of modern social psychology. At the same time, certain aspects of family life were studied by scientists from different perspectives, which made it possible to reveal the essence of this phenomenon and form relevant definitions. For example, today, family life, moving in terms of its content, undergoes serious changes along with the development of society. directly related to the change. Family life appears as an important sphere of a person's life activity, determines the quality of his life in general, and appears as a force that activates his development as a person. In the framework of this study, family life is defined as a separate relationship between family members (married partners, children, relatives) characterized by the commonality of the place of residence, marriage, interests, feelings, general well-being and prosperity. it implies an understanding of the complex, multifaceted system of relationships and connections.

LIST OF REFERENCES USED

1. Karimova V.M. The formation of social ideas about the family among Uzbek youth. Dissertation written for obtaining the scientific degree of doctor of psychological sciences. - T.: 1994. - 312 p.
2. Razakova R.S. Peculiarities of successful and unsuccessful family members. 2 Journal of integrative psychology . Vypusk 30 chast 2. 2023 file:///C:/WINDOWS/Temp/Rar\$DIa7408.49888/%D0%A0%D0%B0%D0%B7%D0%B0%D0%BA%D0%BE%D0%B2%D0%B0%20%D0%A0.%D0%A1.%D0%92%D0%B5%D1%81%D1%82%D0%BD%D0%B8%D0%BA%202023-30 -2.pdf
3. Shoumarov G ' .B. "Family psychology". Study guide for students of academic lyceums and vocational colleges . - T.: Sharq , 2000. - 65 p.
4. Saidmuratova MB In children book to study interest of formation psychological features . - Psychol . fb ... Ph.D teeth _ Autorefer - T.: TDPU, 2023, - 22 p. <http://library.ziyonet.uz/uz/book/127434>
5. Rakhimova ER, Teenager communication psychological difficulties diagnosis and correction . - Psychol . fb ... Ph.D teeth _ Autorefer - T.: TDPU, 2023, - 19 p. <http://library.ziyonet.uz/uz/book/127453>
6. Sherzhanova N. _ PERSONALITY PROYAVLENIYA ADAPTATsII U DETEY-PODROSTKOV RODITELEY TRUDOVOY MIGRATSII . VESTNIK INTEGRATIVNOY PSYCHOLOGY Vypusk 30. Chast 1. 2023 file:///C:/WINDOWS/Temp/Rar\$DIa7408.49888/%D0%A0%D0%B0%D0%B7%D0%B0%D0%BA%D0%BE%D0%B2%D0%B0%20%D0%A0.%D0%A1.%D0%92%D0%B5%D1%81%D1%82%D0%BD%D0%B8%D0%BA%202023- 30-2.pdf